

REPORT CARD 2026

NEURODEVELOPMENTAL AND HEARING DISORDERS – PART 1

Diego Lourenço dos Santos Silva, Piotr Henryk Skarzynski
and Milaine Dominici Sanfins

ŚWIATOWE CENTRUM SŁUCHU
INSTYTUTU FIZJOLOGII I PATOLOGII SŁUCHU

Journal of
**Hearing
Science**

NEURODEVELOPMENTAL AND HEARING DISORDERS - PART 1

Diego Lourenço dos Santos Silva, Piotr Henryk Skarzynski and Milaine Dominici Sanfins

With this bulletin we are starting a series entitled **"NEURODEVELOPMENTAL AND HEARING DISORDERS"**. In this first part, we address the fundamental aspects of neurodevelopmental disorders and how auditory aspects can affect them. This bulletin provides a broad context and will serve as a basis for the next bulletins. We invite you to join us on this journey.

CHILD DEVELOPMENT

Difficulties with neurodevelopment can interfere with how a child develops at various stages of life. Development happens gradually but is marked by important stages, known as developmental milestones, which involve:

- Cognitive skills;
- Motor skills;
- Social skills.

When these milestones appear within the expected period, the child is considered to have typical development. This concept refers to patterns considered normal in terms of growth, maturation, and behavior for each age group (Zubler, 2022).

Child development occurs spontaneously, manifesting itself in milestones such as gait and language. With maturation, activities become more complex and organized, allowing the child to establish deeper and more structured interactions with the external environment and with their peers.

On the other hand, when the skills expected for child development do not manifest in the expected time, this can light up a warning sign. The persistence of these difficulties throughout development may indicate the presence of a neurodevelopmental disorder.

WHAT ARE NEURODEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS?

Neurodevelopmental disorders correspond to a group of conditions that begin in childhood and affect brain development, resulting in difficulties in essential areas (DSM-5-TR; Olson et al., 2024) such as:

- Cognition;
- Attention;
- Learning;
- Social communication.

THE HETEROGENEITY OF NEURODEVELOPMENTAL DISORDERS

Neurodevelopmental Disorders (NDDs) do not present in a standardized way, but rather in a spectrum of wide variability. Thus, two individuals with the same diagnosis can present completely different experiences and challenges.

LEVELS OF IMPACT AND MANIFESTATION

For a better understanding, we can divide these manifestations into two large groups:

- **Specific Difficulties:** Focus on specific domains, such as reading and writing (learning) or failures in executive control (working memory, attention, and impulse control).
- **Comprehensive Impairment:** Cases in which barriers extend to cognition affecting intellectual autonomy and reciprocity in social interactions.

For this reason, diagnosis is not always simple. However, the earlier the identification, the greater the opportunities for monitoring the clinical picture.

CLASSIFICATION CATEGORIES

Neurodevelopmental disorders are classified into six major categories following the diagnostic manuals widely used in the health area. These categories help to understand the different types of difficulties that can arise during child development. **They are:**

01. Intellectual Developmental Disorder;
02. Communication Disorders;
03. Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD);
04. Specific Learning Disorder;
05. Motor Disorders;
06. Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD).

In the vast majority of individuals these disorders are co-existing. In this way, an individual can present both Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and Intellectual Development Disorder (IDD). Due to the high frequency of comorbidities, the diagnosis should be made sparingly using validated and reliable instruments and by qualified interdisciplinary professionals.

INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENTAL DISORDER

Intellectual development disorder is characterized by its onset in childhood and whose alterations (deficits) encompass intellectual and adaptive functioning with a focus on the conceptual, social, and practical domains. As with other developmental disorders, the diagnosis of intellectual disability has specific criteria for a diagnosis to be confirmed:

- **Criterion A:** refers to deficits in intellectual functions, including alterations in reasoning, planning, judgment, abstract thinking, and learning.
- **Criterion B:** refers to deficits in adaptive functioning, evidenced by difficulties in meeting developmental and sociocultural standards of personal independence and social responsibility.
- **Criterion C:** establishes that such alterations are present during the period of child development.

COMMUNICATION DISORDERS

Communication disorders involve deficits related to speech, language, and communication. Although these terms are interconnected, they should not be used synonymously, as they have distinct and complementary definitions. Below, we review each of them.

- **LANGUAGE:** refers to the use of a conventional system of symbols, organized into words and phrases, with the purpose of transmitting ideas and information, which can occur in spoken, written, or signed form.
- **SPEECH:** refers to the production of vocal sounds and involves aspects such as articulation, fluency, voice, and resonance.
- **COMMUNICATION:** This is a broader concept, which encompasses all verbal and non-verbal means used for the transmission of information and ideas. Thus, it can be said that speech and language are components of the communicative process.

IS THERE ANY KIND OF CATEGORIZATION OF COMMUNICATION DISORDERS?

The category of communication disorders includes:

- Language disorder, speech sound disorder;
- Childhood-onset fluency disorder (stuttering);
- Social Communication Disorder (Pragmatics);
- Developmental Language Disorder (LDD).

ATTENTION DEFICIT HYPERACTIVITY DISORDER (ADHD)

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by a persistent pattern of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity that affects the development and functioning of the individual.

The characteristics of inattention in ADHD are manifested by behaviors such as:

- **Deviating from tasks;**
- **Failing to follow instructions or completing work;**
- **Have difficulty staying focuse;**
- **Being disorganized.**

It is important to mention that such actions are not attributable to challenging behaviors or a lack of understanding.

AND WHAT ABOUT HYPERACTIVITY?

Hyperactivity is related to excessive motor activity in situations where it is not appropriate, such as:

- Excessive agitation;
- Repetitive movements;
- Loquacity (the characteristic of those who speak a lot, with an abundance of words and fluidity, that is, it is related to quantity);

In adults, hyperactivity can manifest as extreme restlessness or as a pattern of behavior that burdens people around them.

Impulsivity refers to hasty actions performed without premeditation, which may represent risk or harm to the individual.

SPECIFIC LEARNING DISORDER

Specific Learning Disorder (SLD) is categorized as a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by persistent difficulties related to various academic domains, mainly:

- Reading;
- Writing;
- Mathematics.

Their academic skills are below what is expected for the individual's age group and school year.

Its definition is related to learning difficulties that do not stem from lack of access to academic content or inadequate educational opportunities.

An interesting aspect is that they can coexist with other disorders, such as Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and Developmental Language Disorder (DLD).

ASD presents a set of clinically assessed symptoms, in which the individual may present:

- Slow or inaccurate word reading and with effort;
- Difficulty in understanding what is read;
- Spelling difficulties;
- Impairments in writing;
- Difficulties in number sense;
- Difficulties in mathematical reasoning.

Above all, the difficulties observed in ASD show alterations in phonological processing, with greater impairment in the domain of phonological awareness.

COMPONENTS OF PHONOLOGICAL PROCESSING?

01. PHONOLOGICAL AWARENESS

It is related to the ability to perceive, recognize and manipulate the sounds of speech associated with graphemes (in the process of decoding and encoding).

02. PHONOLOGICAL MEMORY

Phonological memory can be divided into two types: short-term phonological memory, responsible for the temporary storage of information, and working phonological memory, related to the active manipulation of phonological information.

03. FAST AUTOMATED NAMING

Rapid automated naming (NAR) is a cognitive-linguistic skill that refers to the ability to quickly and efficiently access and retrieve phonological and semantic information stored in the mental lexicon.

In general, the difficulties associated with ASD are first observed at the beginning of formal schooling; however, they may not fully manifest in this period, becoming more evident as academic demands increase and, thus, begin to exceed the limited capacities of the individual in the affected skills.

MOTOR DISORDERS

Neurodevelopmental motor disorders include:

- Developmental coordination disorder;
- Stereotyped movement disorder;
- Tic disorders.

Developmental coordination disorder is characterized by difficulties in the acquisition and execution of motor skills, and is observed as clumsiness, slowness or imprecision in movements. These difficulties interfere with activities of daily living.

Stereotyped movement disorder occurs when the individual has repetitive movements with no clear purpose, such as clapping their hands, swaying their body, hitting their head, or biting themselves. **These behaviors can interfere with social, school, or other activities. When there is a risk of self-injury, this should be indicated in the diagnosis.**

Tic disorders are characterized by the presence of motor or vocal tics, which consist of sudden, rapid, repetitive, and non-rhythmic movements or sounds.

AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is classified as a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by persistent deficits in social communication and social interaction in multiple contexts.

These deficits involve the following losses:

- In socio-emotional reciprocity;
- In the non-verbal communicative behaviors used for social interaction;
- In skills related to the development, maintenance and understanding of relationships.

Concomitantly, individuals with ASD have more restricted behaviors and interests that may include:

- Repetitive movements (stereotypies);
- Difficulty in dealing with changes in routine;
- Intense focus on specific subjects;
- Increased or decreased sensitivity to sounds, lights, and textures.

A diagnosis of Autism Spectrum Disorder is based on the identification of these clinical manifestations, taking into account individual variability in the presentation of symptoms.

In addition, there are other points to be analyzed to define the clinical picture, such as the presence of associated conditions (such as, for example, the existence of associated comorbidities) and the level of severity of symptoms (which is defined based on the degree of support needed by the individual).

In the next bulletins we will address each disorder and its relationship with the auditory system. We invite you to join us on this journey of exploring neurodevelopmental and hearing disorders. If you are interested in reading about a specific subject, send a message to msanfins@uol.com.br

Quiz - Neurodevelopmental Disorders

1. What are the three major areas that make up the milestones of child development?

- a) Auditory, visual, and motor skills.
- b) Cognitive, motor, and social skills.
- c) Linguistic, emotional, and physical skills.
- d) Adaptive, conceptual, and practical skills.

2. According to the text, into how many categories are Neurodevelopmental Disorders classified according to diagnostic manuals?

- a) Four categories.
- b) Eight categories.
- c) Six categories.
- d) Three categories.

3. Criterion B for the diagnosis of Intellectual Disability (ID) refers to:

- a) Deficits in intellectual functions, such as reasoning and planning.
- b) Deficits in adaptive functioning, with difficulties in personal independence and social responsibility.
- c) Onset of the changes during adulthood.
- d) Presence of repetitive and stereotyped behaviors.

4. Which of the following alternatives is NOT included among the types of Communication Disorders listed in the text?

- a) Childhood-onset fluency disorder (stuttering).
- b) Autism spectrum disorder.
- c) Social (pragmatic) communication disorder.
- d) Speech sound disorder.

5. In ADHD, hyperactivity may manifest in adults as:

- a) Difficulty maintaining focus and completing tasks.
- b) Stereotyped movements and vocal tics.
- c) Extreme restlessness or behavior that causes strain on people around them.
- d) Slowness and inaccuracy in movements.

6. Which of the following correctly describes Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) as presented in the text?

- a) It is characterized exclusively by difficulties in reading and writing.
- b) It presents persistent deficits in communication and social interaction, along with restricted behaviors and interests.
- c) It is defined by repetitive movements without impairment in social communication.
- d) It begins exclusively in adulthood and affects only cognition.

Correct Answers to the Quiz:

- 1. Correct answer: b
- 2. Correct answer: c
- 3. Correct answer: b
- 4. Correct answer: b
- 5. Correct answer: c
- 6. Correct answer: b

REFERENCES CONSULTED:

01. Zubler JM, Wiggins LD, Macias MM, Whitaker TM, Shaw JS, Squires JK, Pajek JA, Wolf RB, Slaughter KS, Broughton AS, Gerndt KL, Mlodoch BJ, Lipkin PH. Evidence-informed milestones for developmental surveillance tools. *Pediatrics*. 2022; 149(3):e2021052138. doi:10.1542/peds.2021-052138.
02. American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders: Fifth Edition, Text Revision (DSM-5-TR)*. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Association Publishing; 2022.
03. Olson L, Bishop S, Thurm A. Differential diagnosis of autism and other neurodevelopmental disorders. *Pediatr Clin North Am*. 2024; 71(2):157-177. doi:10.1016/j.pcl.2023.12.004.
04. World Health Organization. *International Classification of Diseases, 11th Revision (ICD-11). Clinical Descriptions and Diagnostic Guidelines for Mental, Behavioural or Neurodevelopmental Disorders*. Geneva: WHO; 2022.
05. Gomez R, Chen W, Houghton S. Differences between DSM-5-TR and ICD-11 revisions of attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder: a commentary on implications and opportunities. *World J Psychiatry*. 2023; 13(5):138-148. doi:10.5498/wjp.v13.i5.138.
06. Zwaigenbaum L, Penner M. Autism spectrum disorder: advances in diagnosis and evaluation. *BMJ*. 2023; 381:e072286.

Autores

DIEGO LOURENÇO DOS SANTOS SILVA

- Graduated from the Federal University of São Paulo - Paulista School of Medicine.
- Master's student in the Graduate Program in Human Communication Disorders at the Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP).
- Member of the Research Group on Cognition, Wave and Hearing Studies (ECO).

PROF. DR. PIOTR HENRYK SKARZYNSKI

- Professor, Otorhinolaryngologist, Master and Doctor from the Medical University of Warsaw;
- Realiza trabalho científico, didático, clínico e organizacional no World Hearing Center of Institute of Physiology and Pathology of Hearing, Institute of Sensory Organs and Medical University of Warsaw.
- Specialist in otorhinolaryngology, pediatric otorhinolaryngology, speech therapy and public health;
- Participated in the 3rd Consultation Meeting at the World Health Organization (WHO) World Hearing Forum.
- Membro do Roster of Experts on Digital Health da OMS;
- Vice-President and Institutional Representative of ISfTeH;- President-elect of the International Advisory Board of the American Academy of Otolology – Head and Neck Surgery (AAO-HNS);
- Membro do Departamento de Congressos e Reuniões da European Academy of Otolology and Neuro-otology (EAONO), Representante Regional da Europa da International Society of Audiology (ISA), Vice-Presidente do Hearing Group, Auditor da European Federation of Audiology Societies (EFAS), membro do Facial Nerve Stimulation Steering Committee;
- Secretary of the Council of the Polish Society of Otorhinolaryngologists, Phoniaticians and Audiologists. Member of the Audit Committee (2018–2019)
- Goodwill Ambassador representing Poland at the AAO-HNSF 2021 OTO Annual Meeting and Experience and, since 2021, a member of the AAO-HNS Implantable Hearing Devices Committee and the Otolology and Neurotology Education Committee.
- Advisory Committee of International Experts of the CPAM-VBMS, honorary member of the ENT Danube Society and honorary member of the Société Française d'OtoRhino-Laryngologie.
- Member of the Council of the National Science Center.

PROF. DRA. MILAINE DOMINICI SANFINS

- Adjunct Professor in the Hearing Disorders discipline of the Speech-Language Pathology and Audiology Program at the Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP);
- Member of the research group at the Institute of Physiology and Pathology of Hearing and World Hearing Center, Kajetany, Poland;
- Leader of the ECOA research group (Electrophysiology, Cognition, Waves and Hearing), registered with the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq);
- Advisor in the Graduate Program in Human Communication Disorders (PPG-DCH) at the Federal University of São Paulo (UNIFESP);
- Professor in the Clinical Audiology Graduate Program at the Albert Einstein Israeli Institute of Teaching and Research;
- Postdoctoral fellow at the World Hearing Center, Warsaw, Poland;
- Sandwich PhD at the University of Campinas (School of Medical Sciences – FCM-UNICAMP) and at the University of Ferrara, Italy;
- Specialist in Audiology certified by the Federal Council of Speech-Language Pathology and Audiology;
- Bachelor's and Master's degrees from the University of São Paulo (Faculty of Medicine – FMUSP);
- Member of the Teaching and Research Committee of the Brazilian Academy of Audiology (2024–2026);
- Reviewer of scientific articles and book chapters in the fields of Audiology, Electrophysiology, Neuroaudiology, and Neuroscience;
- Instagram: @misanfins | Email: msanfins@uol.com.br | msanfins@unifesp.br